

PROBLEMS OF USING NEW ELECTRICAL INSULATING SYSTEMS AND ELECTRICAL MATERIALS IN POWER TRANSFORMERS**Safiyev E.S.***docent, Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University
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The article discusses the issue of introducing new electrical insulating systems and electrical materials in power transformers. Particular attention is paid to the use of such solid electrical insulating materials as NOMEX and TRANSTERM, as well as eiegaz insulation. The prospects of using superconducting and magnetic materials in transformers are reflected.

Keywords: power transformer, electrical materials, dry transformer, oil transformer, dielectric material

Despite the fact that the manufacturing technology of power transformers has not changed for a long time, scientists and specialists are trying to improve it and are confident that by introducing modern electrical materials they can improve the properties of transformers. But the introduction of new materials into production is perceived ambiguously by transformer manufacturers. This is due to technical and economic considerations. Currently, in developed countries, transformers with solid cast insulation are used and they are gradually replacing oil-insulated transformers produced since the beginning of the last century. The use of NOMEX insulation is considered a major development in electrical insulation technology. NOMEX is a synthetic aromatic material with high dielectric, chemical and mechanical properties. It is used to make paper, cardboard, insulating parts of various configurations and special profiles. NOMEX is non-toxic, resistant to radiation, fire, acids, alkalis, moisture, insects, mold, etc. But this insulation has some disadvantages compared to solid cast insulation. During operation of transformers, NOMEX insulation is destroyed under the influence of dynamic forces arising in the transformer windings, the windings are deformed and bent.

Dry-type transformers use an insulating impregnating system based on mica materials with high pressure and deep vacuum. This insulation is called TRANSTERM. Fiberglass is also used in this insulation along with mica. This makes it possible to create a reliable reinforcement structure and resistance to partial discharges, pulse voltages, and brings the coefficient of linear expansion of the insulation closer to the transformer winding wire. Transformers with TRANSTERM insulation can operate at temperatures from - 65°C to + 55°C. Some performance characteristics are superior to cast resin transformers. Service life 30 years. They also have high environmental properties and fire resistance. When comparing oil transformers and dry transformers, the advantages of the latter in terms of fire resistance and environmental friendliness are clearly noticeable. It is clear that solid dielectric transformers (cast resin, NOMEX, etc.) will gradually replace oil transformers. But such a replacement is still possible in closed electrical substations, because Dry-type transformers are not designed to operate outdoors. Another advantage of cast insulation is its rigid connection to the windings, thereby resisting electrodynamic

forces and maintaining its shape. An analogue of oil transformers operating in the open air are gas-insulated transformers. SF₆ gas is a more efficient dielectric than air and nitrogen. In addition, it is non-flammable and inert. Having high thermal conductivity, SF₆ gas in transformers can be used as a refrigerant, which is its advantage.

Despite the fact that SF₆ gas has been used as a gaseous dielectric for a long time, currently it is most often used in complete distribution devices. SF₆ transformers are more resistant to fire and explosion than oil transformers. In addition, when using SF₆ gas, the weight of some elements is reduced, the current-carrying parts of transformers are effectively cooled, which makes it possible to produce a more compact transformer with light weight.

According to some experts, in the near future traditional cellulose insulation and mineral oils will be used in transformers. They still remain effective and reliable materials. Despite the fact that SF₆ transformers are small in volume and weight, they are very expensive in price, so the need for them is small. But in the future the need for them will increase. The main characteristics that determine the quality of transformer insulation are thermal stability and fire resistance. The first property affects the design solution, weight and volume of the transformer, and the second affects its implementation area. Therefore, in each specific case, during operation it is necessary to focus on optimal technical and economic indicators. If the transformer will be operated indoors, then non-flammable insulation must be used. In open areas or on overhead line supports, oil-immersed transformers should be used until the best new insulation option is installed. Therefore, in the near future it is impossible to abandon oil transformers.

Many European countries, when choosing a dielectric material from the point of view of environmental safety, refuse to use oil transformers. In Russia and some other countries there is no such restriction. Along with this, increasing the production of dry transformers with monolithic insulation and their use in distribution networks is considered very necessary. But in high-voltage lines (110-500 kV) there is still no alternative to oil transformers. Their efficiency is greater than that of dry transformers. Currently, Japan prefers the pro-

duction and implementation of gas-insulated transformers. In Russia, gas-insulated transformers of type TE-4000/35 are being prepared for testing. Such transformers are characterized by their small size, fire resistance, etc. The technology of replacing old oil transformers with SF₆ transformers is very difficult. But when creating new modern digital substations, it is advisable to use SF₆ transformers.

Saving electricity in power transformers is associated with reducing losses. Nowadays, oil transformers with losses of 30% at no-load and 20% at short circuit and a group of efficient dry transformers with cast insulation have been created. In addition, modern transformers are equipped with telemetric devices for possible remote control of oil level, temperature and pressure. In the near future, transformers with a magnetic core made of amorphous steel with a nanocrystalline structure will be produced. The use of amorphous steel will reduce no-load losses by up to 75%. Recently, it has become possible to produce amorphous steel strips with large dimensions for power transformers. But due to their high cost, their implementation is delayed. Scientists are working tirelessly to create high-temperature superconductors and cryoconductors. The use of these materials in transformer windings will greatly improve the performance of transformers.

Conclusions.

1. Oil-filled power transformers are gradually being replaced by dry-type cast resin transformers. At the same time, along with economic feasibility, it is also necessary to take into account the environmental and fire safety of transformers.

2. The production and implementation of gas-insulated transformers is a relevant and promising area of electrical engineering.

3. Application of modern magnetic, high-temperature superconducting and cryoconducting materials in transformers will greatly increase its performance.

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